

Selected Aspects of Teachers' Professional Attitudes towards Inclusive Education

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ABSTRACT. Teachers and their attitudes are essential to implementing inclusive education in mainstream schools. This study focuses on vocational subject teachers and utilises Mahat's (2008) MATIES (Multidimensional Attitudes Toward Inclusive Education Scale) to examine the cognitive, affective, and behavioural dimensions of their attitudes. Results show statistically significant differences according to age and teaching experience, but not gender. A key finding is the existence of a predictive relationship between cognitive and affective components and behavioural intentions. This knowledge can contribute to the successful implementation of changes in the system of inclusive education and embedding inclusive practices in schools,

since understanding teacher attitudes is crucial for transforming traditional schools into inclusive ones, promoting equity, and being willing to tailor their environments to the needs of all students.

KEY WORDS. Inclusive education, vocational subject teachers, SEN students, teachers' professional attitudes, inclusive school environment

INTRODUCTION

Creating inclusive educational environments that provide students with special educational needs opportunities to receive education in mainstream schools is a recent trend in education in many countries, including the Slovak Republic. According to Booth and Ainscow (2000), inclusive schools are safe places where no form of discrimination is tolerated, meaning they respect the principles of equity and accept diversity. UNESCO (2020) emphasises the importance of guaranteeing the presence, active participation, and academic success of all learners, with particular attention to those at risk of marginalisation. Accordingly, the European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education (EASNIE, 2022) emphasises the importance of creating welcoming environments for all learners, which value their diversity and provide them with both academic and social support. The main advantage of inclusive schools is that they promote the well-being of all students, are open and accessible, and are characterised by teachers' collaboration.

Despite the commitment of Member States to the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development to leave no child behind and promote equity in education as part of Sustainable Development Goal 4 (Barnová, Kožuchová, Krásna, & Osad'an, 2022) – the concept of inclusive education remains a widely debated topic among scholars and practitioners as there is not a clearly defined borderline, which would indicate when school inclusion is in the best interest of a particular student and when special education is a more suitable option. Such a situation needs an immediate response as it is alarming. Available data (WHO, 2005; OECDiLibrary, n.d.) show that a long-term significantly increasing trend can be observed in the number of pupils and students requiring the provision of special education or having additional needs, which is also supported by the available data from the Slovak Republic, where in the school year 2024/25, 31,170 diagnosed SEN students studied in special schools and 50,356 SEN students attended mainstream schools, while in 1996, 30,736 SEN students attended special schools and only 8,050 SEN students were integrated and studies with their non-SEN peers. It is interesting that in 1996, only 3,451 students were reported as integrated (the

term inclusion was not used in official data) into mainstream schools (CVTI SR, Štatistická ročenka – Statistical Yearbook). In compliance with the philosophy of inclusive education, educational systems are responsible for creating favourable conditions for SEN students who should be educated together with their intact peers. Undoubtedly, it is a challenge for both governments and schools; however, in most countries, experts consider inclusive education beneficial for all stakeholders, and therefore, it is prioritised.

Many recent studies have confirmed an increasing trend in enrolling SEN students in mainstream education. For instance, in the United Kingdom, a 26% increase in the ratio of SEN students was recorded between years 2022 and 2023 (National Audit Office, 2024). Similarly, UNESCO (2024) reported a substantial global increase in the placement of SEN students in mainstream school settings, with figures rising from 2% in 1989 to 66% in 2020.

In Slovakia, in the context of the 2030 Agenda implementation, “Education for Life of Dignity” is among the six declared national priorities, as well as “Good Health”. These include the goal of “Strengthening the principles of inclusion in the education system and ensuring equal opportunities for all children, pupils, and students, regardless of their social background, disability or nationality/ethnicity, with an emphasis on increasing opportunities for the application of positive social mobility”. This national priority supports Sustainable Development Goals 4, 8, and 10, and in compliance with it, inclusive practices should be applied in education. Although Slovakia, in 2015, along with 192 other countries, adopted the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, the Slovak school legislation was amended relatively recently, in January 2022. As a consequence, the inclusive education concept lacked a formal legislative basis for implementing its principles, and so the older concept of school integration was applied in schools. However, it must be noted that there were several initiatives targeted at introducing the principles of inclusive education even before the term school inclusion was defined in the School Act, e.g. Modern and Successful Slovakia (Moderné a úspešné Slovensko, 2020) or the national Strategy for Applying an Inclusive Approach in Education (Stratégia inkluzívneho prístupu vo výchove a vzdelávaní). Moreover, scholars have advocated for the transformation of the traditional schools into inclusive educational environments. Despite all the existing efforts, as the results of previously published research studies conducted in the Slovak Republic show, teacher attitudes towards inclusive education vary (e.g., Čepelová, 2020a, b).

Previously conducted research in the field (see e.g. Van Steen & Wilson, 2020; Barnová et al., 2022) has demonstrated that teachers’ personalities, their professional preparedness, attitudes towards inclusive education, and also openness to pedagogical innovation are critical factors in embedding

inclusive principles in schools. Consequently, gathering empirical data on these phenomena is important, as it can provide experts and policymakers with reliable information, helping them to make informed decisions and implement effective strategies. The present study aims to fill the gap in existing knowledge by investigating Slovak teachers' attitudes towards inclusive education and the direction of the associations between the cognitive, affective, and behavioural components of their attitudes.

SCHOOL INCLUSION VS. SCHOOL INTEGRATION

The major problem in creating inclusive school environments is that a group of teachers and school leaders still do not recognise the difference between school integration and school inclusion. They perceive this shift as a change in terminology to be “politically correct”, which does not require a change in their approach to teaching. Daniels and Gardner (2000) emphasise that it must lead to a significant change in perspective, as school integration is based on the premise that SEN students are different from their intact peers, which brings specific problems. However, inclusive schools recognise that challenges in education are not inherent to students themselves but are rooted in institutional structures and societal attitudes toward inclusion. This perspective reflects a shift in the paradigm – from a deficit-oriented model to a social model of education, which emphasises the need for a systemic change and the removal of barriers within the school environment. Following Ainscow (1995), school integration can be characterised as making specific additional arrangements for SEN students as individuals to help them fit into the existing school environment. Fredricson and Cline (2015) point out that it is a process of assimilation and put it in contrast with creating inclusive schools, which can be characterised by restructuring the school environment and radically changing or modifying the school's work. According to them, in inclusive schools, the educational work is tailored to meet their students' needs and a favourable school climate is created in which all students are accepted.

A meta-analysis conducted in the USA by Kalamouka et al. (2007) revealed that 26 analysed research studies examining the impact of inclusive practices in education, based on a comparison of performance criteria, provided evidence that inclusive educational practices are equally beneficial for SEN and non-SEN students. Similar results were found in the Slovak conditions as well (e.g. Porubčanová & Dolinská, 2021). Moreover, recent studies also confirm that inclusion fosters empathy and positive attitudes among non-SEN students. An increased level of understanding of the concept of diversity can characterise them; they are more tolerant, have more developed social skills (Kart & Kart, 2021), and have more open attitudes towards diversity (Molina Roldán et al., 2021). On the other hand, the philosophy of school inclusion

does not deny the role of special schools; instead, it considers placing students in them the final option in cases where studying together with peers in mainstream schools is not possible. Students should be enrolled in special schools or classrooms solely based on thorough and accurate diagnostic assessments, indicating that such placement should be reserved for exceptional circumstances.

TEACHER ATTITUDES TOWARDS INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

The growing emphasis on creating inclusive education systems has highlighted the importance of researching attitudes towards inclusive education. Teachers are among the most significant factors influencing the quality and effectiveness of education, as well as their students' cognitive, social, and mental development, which was confirmed by Van Kessel et al. (2021), who underscored the role of teachers in educating SEN students. It can be assumed that their knowledge, skills, and professional competencies, as well as their attitudes and opinions, affect students' value orientation, well-being, school and life satisfaction, and their performance both in and outside the school environment. This is consistent with Wächter et al. (2024), suggesting that favourable teacher attitudes towards school inclusion can be associated with student well-being. Additionally, teacher attitudes influence the overall functioning of schools and impact the success of implementing innovations. Teachers' openness towards innovations or introducing changes can be decisive when building inclusive educational environments and also determines the quality of the implementation of the principles of inclusive education, which is supported by a whole range of international research studies (e.g. Schulze et al., 2019; Van Steen & Wilson, 2020; Mouchritsa et al., 2022; Fu et al., 2021), but also research studies carried out in the Slovak educational environment (see e.g. Lajčin, 2021; Barnová et al., 2021).

Van Steen and Wilson (2020) pointed out the role of class teachers (a term used in the Slovak educational context). They claimed that the success or failure of implementing inclusive practices is determined by the efforts teachers make to adapt the classroom to the needs of SEN students. They also found no association between teachers' attitudes towards placing health-disadvantaged students in mainstream schools and cultural or demographic factors. Schulze et al. (2019) examined the associations between teachers' attitudes towards inclusive education and their explicit attitudes towards health-disadvantaged individuals, revealing strong correlations. They highlighted the pivotal role teachers play in delivering effective education to SEN students. Secondary school teachers' attitudes and self-efficacy were studied by Opoku et al. (2020), who found that these are among the determinants of teachers' willingness to employ inclusive strategies in education in Ghana. Between teachers' attitudes and their subjective norms,

no associations were found. Strakšienė (2020) conducted a qualitative study examining the association between music teachers' age and their attitudes towards inclusive education. Their findings showed that older teachers were more sceptical about implementing inclusive principles in their teaching in contrast to less experienced or younger peers. What is interesting is that older teachers had problems working in teams and sharing their experiences or examples of good practice with their peers. Raguindin et al. (2020) investigated the Southeast Asian environment, studying the inclusive procedures applied by teachers. They observed that despite more than two decades having passed since the adoption of the Salamanca Statement – which affirms that (1) schools must meet all children's need regardless of their physical, intellectual, emotional, linguistic, or other characteristics, and (2) implementing inclusive principles in mainstream classrooms is the most effective means of fostering an inclusive society (UNESCO, 1994) – marginalisation and discrimination in education remain persistent issues.

METHODS AND RESEARCH INSTRUMENTS

To explore vocational subject teachers' attitudes toward inclusive education, the study employed the standardised Multidimensional Attitudes Toward Inclusive Education Scale (MATIES) developed by Mahat (2008). The research tool consists of 18 items and the respondents indicate their answers utilising a 6-point Likert scale, with responses ranging from completely agree (1) to completely disagree (6). Based on Fazio and Olson's (2003) three-factor theoretical model, the items in the questionnaire saturate the 1. cognitive; 2. affective; and 3. behavioural aspects of teachers' attitudes. The cognitive aspect reflects teachers' thoughts, ideas, perceptions, opinions or beliefs about inclusive education, which serve as important determinants of the quality of their pedagogical practices with SEN students. The affective aspect captures teachers' emotional responses and feelings associated with the concept of inclusion, i.e. their openness and motivation to use inclusive practices in part of their everyday work. Lastly, the behavioural dimension shows teachers' intentions to act in desirable ways in inclusive settings, helping to evaluate their readiness to implement inclusive strategies and practices and adapt their teaching to learners' diverse needs. Among the 18 inclusion indicators (items), six items address each of the dimensions.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The research study and all the applied procedures were conducted in compliance with the Declaration of Helsinki's ethical standards. The research participants were informed about the nature of the research study and participated in it voluntarily. Informed consent was obtained from all participants. All data were anonymised to ensure confidentiality and to

protect participants' privacy. Ethical approval was granted by The Board for Internal System of Quality Assurance of DTI University, Slovakia, in compliance with the Code of Ethics of DTI University, Slovakia.

RESEARCH SAMPLE

In the research sample, 257 vocational subject teachers from Slovakia were included, which, taking into account the specifics of the target group, can be considered a sufficient number. In the context of the data presented below, the demographic data shown in Tables 1, 2, and 3 are important.

Table 1 Composition of the research sample according to respondents' gender

		N	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Valid	Females	156	60.7	60.7	60.7
	Males	101	39.3	39.3	100.0
	Total	257	100.0	100.0	

Source: Authors

Table 2 Composition of the research sample according to respondents' age

		N	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Valid	23 – 47 years	125	48.6	48.6	48.6
	48 – 72 years	132	51.4	51.4	100.0
	Total	257	100.0	100.0	

Source: Authors

Table 3 Composition of the research sample according to respondents' teaching experience

		N	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Valid	3 months – 18 years	129	50.2	50.2	50.2
	19 – 43 years	128	49.8	49.8	100.0
	Total	257	100.0	100.0	

Source: Authors

RESEARCH RESULTS

In the initial phase of data analysis, the variables of gender, age, and length of teaching experience were examined to identify the existence of any associations between them and the three dimensions of the MATIES questionnaire. Subsequently, these data were used as the basis for further data analysis, intending to reveal other, less frequently explored aspects of teachers' attitudes towards inclusive education.

FOUNDATIONS FOR IN-DEPTH DATA ANALYSIS

1. Gender-related peculiarities of teacher attitudes towards inclusive education

In one of the formulated research hypotheses, the existence of statistically significant differences in the attitudes towards inclusive education between male and female vocational subject teachers were presumed. The obtained results did not reveal any statistically significant differences according to the variable of gender in any of the dimensions.

2. Age-related peculiarities of teacher attitudes towards inclusive education

The results related to the variable of age where the sample was dichotomised (teachers in the 48 – 72 age range and teachers in the age range 23 – 47) revealed statistically significant differences in the scores for two of the three dimensions – the behavioural and the affective dimensions, which show that the group of younger participants (in the 23 – 47 age range) demonstrated more negative attitudes towards inclusive education than their older colleagues (aged between 48 and 72 years). The performed data analysis revealed no statistically significant differences in the cognitive dimension.

3. Teaching experience and its impact on teacher attitudes towards inclusive education

Regarding the variable of teaching experience, statistically significant differences were observed in the affective and behavioural dimensions. Consistent with the findings for the age variable, no statistically significant differences were found in the cognitive dimension. In both the affective and behavioural components, teachers with shorter teaching experience (varying from 3 months up to 18 years) demonstrated significantly more negative attitudes compared to their more experienced counterparts.

EXAMINING THE DIRECTION OF ASSOCIATIONS

Based on the above findings and the statistically significant correlations revealed between the presented variables, the direction of the found associations was examined at the next stage of data analysis. A regression analysis was performed, as the regressors can explain the behaviour of dependent variables and serve as predictors. The performed regression analysis provided additional information. The variables of age, gender, and teaching experience were used to model the behavioural dimension. Considering that the score for the behavioural dimension is a numerical variable, the generalised Poisson regression model was used (see Tables 4 and 5).

Table 4 Deviance residuals

Deviance residuals	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-2.3901	-1.2219	-0.2164	0.8064	5.5712

Source: Authors

Table 5 GLM – generalized linear model

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)	Significance
Intercept	2.6283622	0.1844179	14.252	<2e-16	0
Age	0.0000502	0.0046602	0.011	0.991	0.1
Teaching experience	-0.0060992	0.0046183	-1.321	0.188	0.1
Gender	0.0039028	0.0542857	0.072	0.943	0.1

Source: Authors

As shown in Table 5, none of the three regressors has a significant regression correlation coefficient. The p-values of the regression coefficients for the variables of age and gender are very high, and the p-value for teaching experience is also high. For this reason, the model could not be used. Therefore, the behavioural dimension was examined in relation to regressors – the cognitive dimension and the affective dimension (see Tables 6 and 7).

Table 6 Deviance residuals

Deviance residuals	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
	-3.1016	-1.1045	-0.1669	0.7181	3.8593

Source: Authors

Table 7 GLM – generalized linear model

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)	Significance
Intercept	2.749181	0.135930	20.225	< 2e-16	0
Cognitive dimension – score	0.019853	0.006675	2.974	0.00322	0.001
Affective dimension – score	-0.027132	0.003533	-7.679	3.47e-13	0

Source: Authors

The regression coefficients of the score for the cognitive dimension and the score for the affective dimension are statistically significant. When working with logarithmic regression coefficients, backward exposure was used (see Table 8).

Table 8 Result of backward exposure

Intercept	Cognitive dimension - score	Affective component - score
15.6298261	1.0200514	0.9732324

Source: Authors

The 95% confidence intervals of the regression coefficients are displayed in Table 9.

Table 9
95% confidence intervals of the regression coefficients

	2.5%	97.5%
Intercept	11.9567986	20.3717342
Cognitive component - score	1.0067802	1.0334721
Affective component - score	0.9665164	0.9799975

Source: Authors

The percentage of variability explained by the model is 19.26%, indicating that the model accounts for only a small portion of the variability, leaving approximately 80.74% unexplained.

DISCUSSION

The findings of the present research study suggest that, according to the teachers' beliefs examined in the cognitive dimension of the scale, inclusive classrooms are beneficial for all students, as adapted curricula and inclusive school environments enable them to experience success and promote positive, socially acceptable behaviour. This is supported by the findings of Schulze et al. (2019), Van Steen and Wilson (2020), Mouchritsa et al. (2022), and Fu et al. (2021). An unpleasant yet significant finding in the context of transitioning traditional schools toward inclusive education is that the participating teachers advocated for the existence of special schools, as they were concerned that in mainstream schools, SEN students might be rejected by their intact classmates. Certain groups of teachers hold the belief that students with severe special educational needs should not be enrolled in mainstream schools and teachers' ambivalent attitudes were reported in Bangladesh (Malak & Tasnuba, 2018), in Spain (Lacruz-Pérez, Sanz-Cervera, & Tárraga-Mínguez, 2021), in Finland (Saloviita, 2020), in Czechia (Vad'urová & Pančocha, 2023), in Netherlands (Tenback, De Boer, & Bijstra, 2024), in Central Asian countries Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, and Uzbekistan (Prisiazhniuk, Makoelle, & Zangieva, 2024), or China (Deng et al., 2024).

In the research sample, statistically significant differences emerged between teachers aged 48 and above and those aged 47 and below. Older teachers are less confident when communicating with SEN students and more often experience helplessness when teaching in mixed-ability classrooms compared with younger teachers, which can also explain why they expressed greater dissatisfaction with the placement of all SEN students in mainstream classrooms. This is in line with Strakšienė (2020), Krásna and Čepelová's (2020), Saloviita's (2020) and Deng et al.'s (2024) findings, whose results

showed that older teachers, when compared with their younger or less experienced colleagues, would place SEN students in special schools more frequently. On the other hand, in the present study, the group of older teachers showed a greater openness to modifying classroom communication strategies, as well as the curriculum and assessment criteria, and adapting the physical classroom environment to meet all SEN students' needs. In comparison, younger teachers would rather provide them with assistance. Younger teachers demonstrated more favourable attitudes regarding the inclusive participation of all SEN students in every aspect of classroom life (including social and educational activities) compared to their older counterparts.

The statistically significant differences identified based on teaching experience can be explained by fewer opportunities to work with SEN students and try out various methods of teaching in diverse classrooms provided to less experienced teachers, and, thus, they may have had to cope with more anxiety when teaching in mixed-ability classrooms. In comparison, for more experienced teachers, their experiences can be considered a stabilising factor.

An important finding regarding the significance of the results is that the cognitive and affective dimensions can serve as predictors of the behavioural aspects of teachers' attitudes towards inclusive education. The covariance between subscales suggested a positive correlation, which means that teachers with positive affective and cognitive aspects of their attitudes tend to act or react in a manner that promotes or improves inclusive education. In contrast, the behaviour of teachers with negative affective and cognitive aspects of their attitudes represents an obstacle to the application of inclusive education principles. It is worth noting that attitudes do not always align with behaviour. As confirmed by several studies, behavioural intention is strongly influenced by societal norms governing behaviour, i.e. with what an individual is expected to do by society (Mahat, 2008). In schools that do not actively promote inclusive education, even teachers with positive attitudes toward inclusion may exhibit negative behaviours.

Furthermore, Barnes and Gaines (2015) found that participants expressed the most positive attitudes in the behavioural dimension; however, this dimension reflects what they would like to do rather than what they actually can do. The above also indicates that the cognitive and affective components of teachers' attitudes towards inclusive education can serve as predictors of their behavioural intentions. Our findings align with this, showing that among vocational subject teachers in Slovakia, their behavioural attitudes can be anticipated based on their cognitive and affective attitudes toward inclusion. Given that this area remains relatively underexplored, ongoing research is

focusing on the impact of attitudes, subjective norms, and control on behavioural intentions, utilising the MATIES scale with a larger sample.

The above-presented findings deserve increased attention and provide a basis for further research activities in the field, as they have the potential to contribute to the efficient realisation and application of suggested changes in the system of inclusive education in schools in the Slovak Republic.

CONCLUSION

In line with Bertrand (1998), creating inclusive school environments can be categorised as a humanistic movement in education. In Slovakia, although inclusive education was formally incorporated into school legislation in January 2022, its underlying philosophy is not uniformly embraced across all schools. Experience indicates that during the transition from traditional to inclusive schools, school leaders frequently encounter challenges related to teachers' attitudes and approaches towards inclusive education. In this context, it is important to recognise that teacher attitudes can be influenced or shaped; however, school leaders must first possess accurate information about the situation in their school. The findings of the research study underscore the need for considerable work in the field as teachers need more information, which poses a challenge for universities providing undergraduate teacher training programmes, as well as for institutions offering in-service teacher training opportunities. Also, changes on the societal level and especially in the field of the prevailing attitudes towards minorities, including SEN students and students with additional needs, are needed. It is crucial to combat the concept of "otherness", as highlighted by Vašat (2017) and to recognise that diversity in society and the classroom benefits all stakeholders.

The uniqueness of the above-presented data lies in the finding that, based on the cognitive dimension and the affective dimension, the behavioural component of teachers' attitudes towards inclusive education can be predicted. Considering the present study's limitations, specifically the sample size and its composition, which consisted solely of vocational subject teachers, the findings cannot be generalised to the entire teacher population. Therefore, further research involving a larger and more diverse research sample is necessary. Additionally, there is potential to explore other influencing factors related to teachers' attitudes toward inclusive education, such as their overall attitudes toward disadvantaged groups. Since the cognitive and affective components of attitudes can predict behavioural tendencies, these aspects significantly affect whether teachers adopt a pro-inclusive approach.

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